

Machine Learning Utility Assessment for a Greener Universal Healthcare

Motivation

The current landscape of health sciences, particularly in Medicine, is unimaginable without the ubiquitous **need to exploit complex high-dimensional big data**, leading to the growing prominence of **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**¹, exemplified in the Radiology specialty^{2,3}.

This influence spans diverse societal realms, driven by the **success of Machine Learning (ML)** algorithms, notably **Deep Learning (DL)**⁴. This technological evolution has ushered in an era of augmented medicine, wherein professionals benefit from software assistance in diagnosis and decision-making, embodying the principles of Predictive, Preventive, Personalized, Participatory, and Precision Medicine (5P Medicine)^{5,6}.

However, alongside the undeniable clinical advantages of AI^{7,8}, **ethical questions arise**, necessitating thoughtful consideration. The existing literature addressing ethical concerns related to AI in medicine often explores challenges related to transparency, fairness, human-centered technology, sustainability, and inclusion (see 1c and Jia *et al.* [9] for further details on terminology). These ethical considerations are deemed **essential for policymakers**, urging the establishment of regulatory frameworks grounded in such ethical guidelines¹⁰.

Despite this, there exists a notable **gap in the ethical studies** on the global social concern of climate change due to the **carbon footprint**. The healthcare sector already contributes significantly to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions¹¹ without accounting for the integration of AI. The development and lifecycle of AI technologies, particularly DL algorithms, demand substantial energy¹², especially when handling extensive clinical data such as Electronic Health Records (EHR), genetic information, and longitudinal medical imaging studies¹³ (Figure 1a) attached to state-of-the-art (SOTA) ML/DL models. This energy demand directly contributes to the global GHG burden (Figure 1b). Despite the recognized significance of this issue, studies elucidating the energy consumption of AI models in healthcare are sparse (Figure 1c). A comprehensive **analysis** of the delicate balance between **energy consumption and the positive impact on clinical practice** and research is lacking, a critical aspect in aligning with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) definition, which relies on net-zero emissions for Green Universal Healthcare (GUH) since November 2021 **Climate Change Conference (COP26)**¹⁰.

Therefore, it is vital to address the following **research question**:

How can we undertake the joint assessment of clinical/societal benefits and the environmental footprint for the development of SOTA ML models aiming at GUH?

Problem
Importance

Research
Question

Foundational Work

Health Technological Assessments (HTAs) represent the predominant procedures for systematically assess the impact of novel technologies on healthcare¹⁷. Traditionally, these assessments measure the net utility by weighing health benefits against economic costs. The most employed methodology often involves **cost-effective/utility analysis**¹⁸ **guided by** a slight extension of Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) known as Influence Diagrams (ID) (see Figure 2). As a DAG, the ID node links represent the assumed cause-effect relations characterizing the problem (technology under assessment) features. Therefore, aligning with the AI terminology, we referred to them as **Causal IDs (CIDs)**¹⁹. Unlike general DAGs, CIDs explicitly represent critical features in the decision-making process, denoted by square shapes, demanding strategic choices. The remaining round nodes depict random variables (*rv*), some of them interpreted as costs or utilities (coloured in Figure 2). In a simplified yet widely applied methodology across disciplines, each *rv* is characterized by the simple conditional probability given the nodes influencing them (parent nodes) following the Markov chain rule²⁰, obtained as its frequency on the conditional case from the

Figure 1: Energy-demanding algorithms contribute to Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, a facet often overlooked in ethical guidelines for AI usage in healthcare. **(a)** The computation intensity in GigaFlops per second [GFLOPs] (left *y* axis) executed by state-of-the-art (SOTA) algorithms over recent years (*x*-axis) for medical image segmentation (\diamond). Additional computational demands for biomedical information processing are represented (\circ). The green showcases the computational energy efficiency of SOTA hardware, specifically Graphical Processing Units (GPUs). **(b)** The average carbon intensity (gCO_2/kWh) across the 27 EU countries, their average (EU-27), and Switzerland. **(c)** The number of papers between 2020-2022 addressing key themes related to responsible AI in healthcare. Remarkably, only three of them highlight the imperative to account for GHG emissions (**Social sustainability: GHG**).

observational data or Random Controlled Trials (RCTs) depending on the technology. CIDs greatly facilitate the identification of decision paths and the assignment of utility or cost measures, each weighted by the corresponding chained conditional probability. **In HTAs, costs primarily pertain to economic considerations** (\$) ^{21,22}, while utility in healthcare predominantly involves quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) gained ²³ (years gained per \$). Very recently, there have been advancements in HTAs to incorporate considerations of GHG and the carbon footprint ^{24,25}. This progress involves expanding QALYs units to account for the years gained per \$ invested and the gCO_2/kWh produced by the technology. The integration of the *Life Cycle Assessment* (LCA) standardized method (ISO 14040-44), measuring a product’s environmental impact, plays a pivotal role in this evolution. By integrating the LCA into HTA, stakeholders aspire to broaden the scope of traditional assessments, which typically cover emerging technologies in drug development, surgical interventions, medical devices, etc. These assessments are standard procedures integral to policymaking in both public and private sectors.

Overcoming SOTA Gaps

However, **evaluating ML model development introduces distinct challenges** in addressing our research question. To standardize the HTA methodology for ML model development, considering both its clinical impact and economic and GHG costs, we propose the CID in Figure 2 to model its main components for quantification:

Utility Assessment: In a standard HTA, the QALYs assignment involves measuring the progression of patients treated or intervened with the technology under assessment, aiding in various clinical tasks ²⁶⁻²⁸ (diagnosis, prognosis, symptom evolution, etc.). Different clinical tasks result in varying impacts on QALYs specific to a medical condition. This metric is further weighted by the effectiveness of the technology, often subjectively measured. However, when the technology is an ML model, it can serve multiple clinical tasks. For instance, in oncology, the automated delineation of tumors through radiological images (segmentation) proves valuable for both diagnosis and prognosis. Consequently, and to extend the succinct literature assessing previously developed ML at a single *clinical task*, we will model both the clinical tasks and the *ML model* (technology) as decision nodes. Additionally, the impact on *clinical utility* will hinge on *model performance*, assessable by comparing objective performance

Contribution
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metrics specific to each task²⁹ with baseline models (existing models predating the development of new ones). The conceptualization of these cause-effect relationships is depicted in the green branch at the top of Figure 2.

Carbon Footprint: As previously mentioned, the limited studies applying HTAs to ML models solely consider the economic costs associated with their use (e.g., licensing, maintenance, etc.), as depicted in Figure 2 by the *ML Model* → *Cost*. These studies overlook the vital developmental phase in economic terms, especially in terms of GHG. During this phase, it is imperative to train SOTA models intensively using hardware selected based on the computation and time requirements of each model. The hardware relies on different Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) in setups of varying complexity for optimization but always entails high energy consumption, resulting in specific emissions depending on the *energy source*. Therefore, the LCA required to complement the HTA encompassed in this project will be conducted following current guidelines, which were proven effective recently^{12,30}. This project phase involves using and evaluating software to estimate the carbon footprint^{13,31}, and such tools have also emerged recently, with their application not yet optimized for the clinical environment.

Quantification: Traditional quantification approaches in cost-effective analyses often rely on statistical models like regression, sensitivity analyses, decision trees, or, commonly in HTAs, Markov models. While these models capture statistical associations, they may lack a clear representation of causal relationships and interventions, especially when dealing with hidden confounding variables. This is essential not only for retrospective quantification of models used in clinical settings, addressing uncertainties related to complex *rvs* (e.g., model performance, GHG estimations) but also for assessing the effect of interventions. It enables answering questions like "What is the probability of having this impact if this energy source is used?" and exploring counterfactual scenarios such as "What would have happened if a Y model were used instead of an X?" These considerations are vital in designing experiments and projects. To overcome these challenges, we will employ **Deep Structural Causal Models (DSCMs)**^{32,33} for quantification. DSCMs leverage universal approximators based on DL within a recent research framework demonstrating their ability to precisely represent causal relationships as part of these models.

Contribution

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Figure 2: Causal Influence Diagram (CID) illustrating the inclusion of the *carbon footprint* through the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of *ML models* in Health Technology Assessment (HTA). Squared nodes represent decision-making processes, while round nodes are modeled as random variables (*rv*). Colored nodes highlight the modeled utilities and costs. In green, the *Clinical Utility* is depicted as an effect of the *clinical task* (diagnosis, prognosis, etc.) value in quality-adjusted life years (QALYs)²³ and the estimated *Model Performance*. In red, the *carbon footprint* is represented, accounting for intensive *energy consumption hardware* and the associated *Monetary Cost*.

The powerful theoretical framework that underlies **SCMs enable** modeling³⁴ **causal** relationships between *rvs* based **on observational data**, in contrast to classical **statistical models** that requires frequently unavailable **RCTs**³⁵. RCTs are considered the gold standard for estimating causal effects and can be translated into our model as an **extense grid experiment**^{36,37}, with decision nodes as parameters. Aiming to validate our novel approach, we propose using both: **a) observational data and b) controlled experiments**. To achieve this, leveraging the effectiveness of DL in Radiology for Medical Image Analysis (MIA), we propose model validation in the clinical case of **Multiple Sclerosis (MS)**. MS serves as a paradigmatic example for our objectives, given the challenges associated with its diagnosis, longitudinal evaluation, and prognosis, which are unattainable without the use of Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)³⁸ and intensive DL models^{39,40}. These algorithms facilitate clinical tasks such as detection and segmentation of MS lesions, typically performed by expert neuroradiologists.

For **a)**, we will rely on the multiple reported competitive **challenges**⁴¹⁻⁴³ on DL models' for MS and MRI. This will allow us to gather reliable data on the performance gain provided per model, for the referred clinical tasks and executed on different hardware, enabling us to estimate the average carbon footprint and costs retroactively. For **b)** serving as the gold standard, we will use extensively **manually annotated brain MRI** datasets by expert neuroradiologists to train the models at each experiment. As **SOTA ML models** for medical imaging, we will employ DL algorithms with varying energy and hardware requirements: *UNet*^{44,45}, *UNet++*⁴⁶, *ResNet*⁴⁷, *RetinaNet*⁴⁸, and *TransUNet*⁴⁹. In real-world scenarios, **hardware** options are limited by available resources. To cover a **broad spectrum**, we propose to run experiments on personal computers with a single GPU (e.g., Nvidia[®] RTX3090 and A100), laboratory servers (e.g., employing a single RTX3090, and 2 in 4 multi-GPU configuration), EPFL experimental cloud, and Google Cloud[®] (e.g., employing a single Nvidia[®] H100, 2 RTX H100, and TPUs). The **carbon footprint** will be actively estimated through queries to different **tracking tools**^{13,31} during execution. Additionally, when possible, wattmeters will be used to measure differences between estimates and physical measurements.

The **project** description highlights its **interdisciplinary nature**, aligning well with **E4S**'s requirements.

To accomplish this, hiring a researcher with expertise in developing algorithms for MIA, hardware, and statistical modeling is essential. The researcher would be primarily supervised by the project's Principal Investigator, **Pedro M. Gordaliza**, post-doctoral researcher at the UNIL with extensive experience in DL for MIA and DSCMs⁵⁰⁻⁵³. Additionally, the development and experimental design for MIA algorithms will be provided by **Meritxell Bach Cuadra**, PhD, M.E.R., PD at UNIL and Section Head CIBM SP CHUV-UNIL at Medical Image Analysis Laboratory (**MIAL**). Direct supervision for hardware-related aspects, energy efficiency, and GHG emissions will be overseen by **José Miranda Calero**, Post-Doctoral researcher at the *Embedded Systems Laboratory*(**ESL**) at EPFL, and Professor **David Atienza Alonso**, head of ESL and scientific director of the EPFL **EcoCloud** data-center.

We are confident that the team's collective experience is sufficient to complete the project within one-year, starting in April 2024 under a budget of 84500CHF (details in the budget template). Our intention is to continue this **kick-off project** with SNF support. We aim to disseminate the results through at least one conference proceeding and a paper indexed in a top-tier journal.

Importantly, the proposed project aligns with **E4S**'s mission and its platforms. The approach would be a significant advancement in quantifying the environmental impact of the technological change resulting from the adoption of AI in healthcare models globally. It could provide stakeholders and policymakers with the necessary framework to harness the benefits of AI in reducing healthcare costs while promoting sustainable development. Therefore,

Research
TeamBudget and
OutputE4S Mission
and platforms

the project aligns with several [E4S](#) platforms. Since a specific study of their interactions would require more time than the estimated, we will focus on those that align most closely: *I.1, Environmental policy and strategies*; *II.3, Transforming key industrial sectors: Health and life sciences*; and *III.2, Digitalization, data, and AI*.

Collaborators Check Guidelines and annex

[guidelines](#); [annex](#)

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